

Rethinking Harm to Virtual Characters: Maxims, Indirect Duty, and Dignity in a Kantian Framework

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Abstract

This paper focuses on contemporary controversies surrounding depictions of violations against virtual characters, taking as its point of entry the claim that “virtual characters have no rights, therefore depictions of violating them are not problematic.” It argues that the core issue is not whether virtual characters possess rights, but how the meanings conveyed by such depictions act upon human beings. Drawing on Kantian philosophy, the paper examines the applicability of “indirect duties to animals” to contemporary “virtual characters,” and further proposes that, compared with animals—which Kant regarded as “analogues of humanity”—virtual characters, due to their verisimilitude, can on this basis be regarded as “simulacra of personhood.” Two empirical studies in cognitive science are cited to support this claim. The paper then integrates Kantian and modern social conceptions of “dignity,” arguing that although virtual characters do not possess “dignity” in Kant’s sense, they can nevertheless be normatively presumed to exhibit an internal logic isomorphic to dignity. On this basis, the paper contends that violations against virtual characters manifest as a “downgrading” of the quasi-personhood status they present, and, in a normative sense, reveal that “human dignity” can be detached from “the human.” The paper concludes with the metaphor of the “Ring of Gyges,” suggesting that contemporary virtual space functions like the mythical ring of invisibility.

Keywords: virtual characters; adult anime pornography; Kant; maxims of action; indirect duty; dignity; Ring of Gyges; viewing ethics

Preface

The Global Scale of Anime Culture

Anime culture originated in Japan and, due to its distinctive art style and extensive fan-creation communities, has gradually expanded its influence worldwide. As noted in the 2024 report by the Association of Japanese Animations (AJA), the anime market reached a new peak, with the overseas market share surpassing the domestic Japanese market for the first time (Green Daily, 2024). According to an announcement released by Netflix on September 30, 2025, more than 50% of its members watch anime, with total views exceeding one billion within a year and total viewing time reaching 25 billion hours (Netflix, 2025). The unprecedented enthusiasm for Anime Culture is equally observable offline, as evidenced by the 2024 Anime Expo, which attracted over 407,000 attendees in just four days (Anime Expo, 2024). Hentai, depicting anime pornography, has repeatedly ranked at the top of Pornhub's charts (news.com.au, 2024).

Controversies Regarding Gender Issues: Sexualization and Sexual Violence

However, concurrently, the gender-related issues emerging within Anime Culture have become increasingly prominent, including the deliberate exaggeration of female characters' body proportions, the sexualization of depictions of minors, and the normalization of narratives involving sexual violence against women.

A 2025 content analysis published in *Sex Roles* coded and categorized 30 popular animations, revealing that the majority of samples exhibited phenomena such as revealing and sexually provocative female attire, the male gaze in cinematography, and toxic masculinity. The researchers ultimately concluded that sexualization and sexual objectification of women are pervasive in Japanese anime (Cho, L.Y. et al., 2025).

Furthermore, the study by Tomoya Mukai et al. found that depictions of sexual acts initiated through 'aggressive/intimidating' means are not uncommon in Japanese pornographic manga, and that the prevalence of such initiation methods has significantly increased in recent years (Mukai, T. et al., 2023). Similarly, Connie Bonaros, a member of the Australian Senate, noted during an investigation into Japanese anime and manga publications that 'themes involving minors, incest, rape, sexual abuse, and similar subjects are overwhelmingly numerous.' (ABC News, 2020)

Positive Perspectives on Hentai: The 'Safety Valve' and 'Harmless Virtuality'

With regard to hentai works, some argue that although they contain ethically problematic depictions, they function as a safety valve, allowing men to harmlessly discharge their desires. As columnist John Oberliger contends, the appearance of hentai content enables individuals to satisfy their suppressed, inherently aggressive sexual desires within a safe boundary (Oppliger, 2010). Meanwhile, Saito Tamaki's research and surveys indicate that the vast majority of consumers of anime pornography do not possess the desire to forcibly engage women in sexual intercourse in real life. (Wikipedia contributors, 2025)

But is this really the case? In 19th-century Europe, prostitution was also regarded as a 'necessary evil,' serving to satisfy male sexual desire, maintain men's physical and mental health, and function as a safety valve for releasing drives and regulating sexuality and social order. This perspective was based on the social cognition that 'male desire is irrepressible' (Ripa, Y, 2020). However, from a contemporary standpoint, this view is evidently flawed; desire is not innately beyond control. The 19th-century European understanding of prostitution shares a logical structure with the views represented by John Oberliger on anime pornography, both seeking to justify an acquired desire—subject to environmental influence—as inherently inviolable, described as 'repressed male desire with an inherently aggressive nature.' Based on this cognition, all entities produced to fulfill such desires are consequently granted legitimacy. As a result, the widespread depiction of sexual violence, assault, and humiliation in Anime Pornography has been rhetorically justified as a 'controversial yet necessary' cultural form, sharing its origins with prostitution, historically regarded as a 'necessary evil.'

Concerning the second perspective—that the vast majority of Anime Pornography consumers do not possess the desire to coerce women into sexual relationships in reality—due to the current scarcity of research on hentai, it remains premature to draw definitive conclusions. However, it is clear that there is a positive correlation between the frequency of viewing Anime Pornography and the use of sexual assault strategies (Almeida, 2024). Although the causal relationship remains uncertain, this evidence suffices to refute the argument that the vast majority of consumers of Anime Pornography have no relevant connection to real-world cognition.

“Virtual characters have no rights.”

Yet this explanation alone is incomplete. A significant reason why prostitution is being

reconsidered in contemporary discourse lies in its violation¹ of the human rights principle that “a person must never be treated merely as a means.” Women who, for various reasons, are forced into prostitution—as rational beings—are assigned a price conditionally and deprived of the right to autonomous choice. From the perspective of Immanuel Kant, this constitutes a downgrading from “person” to “thing.”

In the second section of the *Foundations of the Metaphysics of Morals*, Kant states that things (Sachen), as non-rational beings, possess only relative value as means (Kant, 2013, p.47). Regarding the characters in Anime Pornography, regardless of how explicit or extreme their depiction may be, they are clearly not rational beings. Under this premise, it logically follows that there can be no violation of their rights; thus, regarding them as objects of virtual venting appears reasonable.

This reasoning is precisely the defense frequently employed by anime enthusiasts when faced with criticism: virtual portrayals do not directly produce any substantive violation because anime characters are fictional and consequently possess no rights. A typical case cited by Simone Eelmaa in 'Sexualization of Children in Deepfakes and Hentai' concerns a mainstream perspective among anime supporters: 'Drawings do not possess rights, which means they are not legal subjects and therefore do not require legal protection. (Eelmaa, 2022)'

However, does the absence of rights imply that one may arbitrarily project extreme fantasies onto these characters? These characters exhibit human-like appearances and interior emotional portrayals akin to real individuals. Although they are deprived of subjectivity both within and beyond the narrative, such depictions are regarded as a consensual practice within R18 creations. Can this truly be regarded as mere harmless fantasy?

Section One: From the 'Rights Subject' to the 'Maxims of Action'

The rights attributed to virtual characters in this article signify that they do not possess human rights analogous to those of real individuals, rather than implying that their creators lack copyright. Returning to the central issue, the assertion that virtual characters have no rights appears to categorically preclude any further debate. However, this is far from the case. An ancient Chinese poem states, 'After layers of mountains and rivers cause one to doubt there is a path, beyond the dark willows and bright blossoms lies another village,' illustrating that even in seemingly inescapable predicaments, it is possible to discover a new way forward and witness renewal. What awaits us as a hopeful new beginning is to transcend the debate over

¹ In this paper, “violation” does not refer to “rights violation.”

the 'Rights Subject' and turn instead toward a more fundamental inquiry—human nature.

In Kant's most famous formulation of human nature, he states:

"You must act in such a way that you always treat humanity, whether in your own personhood or in that of any other, never merely as a means, but always at the same time as an end."(Kant, 2013, p.48)

In this passage, Kant establishes a practical principle that if a rule must be regarded as supreme, then both one's own humanity and the humanity of others ought to be treated as ends in themselves. This principle not only requires that we refrain from violating the rights of others but also interrogates a more fundamental question—do you accept the concept of 'treating humanity as an end' as a maxim of your action? Kant further states:

'For their value does not lie in the consequences produced, nor in the benefits and uses they provide, but in the intention—that is, in the maxim of the will.' (Kant, 2013, p.53)

In contrast to utilitarians who emphasize the consequences of actions, Kant's evaluation of whether an action is moral centers on whether it is performed from respect for the moral law. If the motive for your action is to seek reward or arises merely from goodwill, Kant holds that these do not necessarily possess moral value. An action that truly has moral value is one that is driven by an internal sense of duty, independent of external contingencies such as the prospect of reward. (Kant, 2013, p.19)

The significance of Kant's statement lies in his shifting the criterion for moral judgment from utilitarian outcomes to the enactment of duty itself. Applied to contemporary virtual games, slaughtering non-player characters (NPCs) within the game incurs no real-world consequences; however, this does not mean it is morally permissible. The critical point is that when a player repeatedly performs this act over time and derives pleasure from such killing, it reveals that the player's mindset has long been habituated to the maxim of 'objectifying humanoid entities as mere tools' in their actions.

Returning to Kant's original discussion of human nature, there is no need to argue whether virtual characters are 'rational beings' or 'subjects of rights,' as the question does not hinge on whether 'rights have been infringed.'The issue rather lies in the fact that when you create, watch, or consume certain content, it reveals the underlying behavioral principles, that is, the maxim you adhere to. This maxim itself constitutes the value upon which judgment is based.

A maxim refers to the principle of action that an individual intends to follow for a given purpose in a particular context. Such a maxim does not necessarily carry inherent moral justification; it should be understood merely as a rule that one establishes for oneself. From Kant's perspective, for a maxim to be morally valid, it must be able to withstand the test of an objective Moral law.

According to the categorical imperative, such a moral maxim ought to be willed as a universal law (Kant, 2013, p.40) and must not entail any contradiction. Moreover, it must not violate the principle of treating oneself and others always simultaneously as ends in themselves, and ultimately, it should be autonomous rather than heteronomous, influenced by desires (Kant, 2013, pp.26-27). One of the fundamental motivations driving players to commit massacres in virtual environments is sensory stimulation; although such stimulation in itself is not inherently problematic, when it serves as the primary rationale for action, it clearly contravenes Kant's requirement for autonomy.

For an action to possess a higher moral value, the agent should act from respect for the moral law, that is, 'Acting from Duty.' Kant further envisioned a scenario wherein an action is performed rightly based on motives such as reputation, compassion, or self-interest; although such actions are not necessarily noble and may lack moral value within Kant's framework, they are not necessarily blameworthy, for regardless of the motive, the action itself is 'in accordance with Duty.' (Kant, 2013, p.20)

What truly opposes 'Acting from Duty' is the 'Violation of Duty (pflichtwidrig),' a behavior that not only lacks moral value but also entails that the agent has degraded their respect for the moral law, yielding it to self-love, inclinations, pleasures, and the like (Kant, 2013, pp.26-27). In the case of slaughtering non-player characters, is it really the case that most players lack moral awareness? This is clearly not so. However, within the game environment, which is constructed and inculcated as 'harmless,' the reverence for moral law is supplanted by the physiological and psychological pleasure derived from virtual killing.

Whether referring to anime characters or the non-player characters mentioned earlier, although none qualify as rational beings, we can assert that such acts of violation against them are, in most instances, devoid of morality. Yet, this inference is grounded primarily in an analysis centered on pleasure as the main motivating factor and has not yet engaged with Kant's reflections on 'humanity, dignity, and personhood.' It is within that framework that we can more deeply critique the claim that 'virtual characters have no rights and therefore may be violated at will.'

Section Two: The Contemporary Turn in Kant's Indirect Duty Theory

As previously noted, for Kant, what matters most is whether the maxim one acts upon respects or violates the moral law, as evident in his account of indirect duties toward non-rational beings (e.g., animals). In the Lectures on Ethics, Kant initially articulates this viewpoint as follows:

“ Animals are analogues of humanity (Analoga der Menschheit) ” (Kant, as cited in Noller, 2021, p. 10; AA 27:1572–1573)

Kant holds that certain behaviors of animals bear a formal resemblance to actions governed by reason in humans, such as exhibiting loyalty toward their master. Therefore, even if we do not strictly have a duty toward them, by performing duties toward them, we are simultaneously fulfilling a duty to ourselves. This is more explicitly demonstrated in the chapter on ‘Virtue’ in the *Metaphysics of Morals*:

‘... all indirectly belong to human duties, that is, concerning these animals; but directly considered, such gratitude is often merely a duty humans owe to themselves.’ (Kant, 2013, p.232)

Furthermore, Kant emphasizes that the act of animal cruelty does not violate duties toward animals (as they lack the capacity for judgment), but rather violates the humanity that one possesses as a rational being. This perspective was subsequently reinforced by Kant, who regarded compassion as an important auxiliary tool in moral practice. He argued that cruelty towards animals simultaneously dulls, progressively weakens, and ultimately extinguishes one’s compassion for the suffering of others (Kant, 2013, pp. 231–232).

In summary, although animals are not rational beings, we nonetheless have indirect duties towards them, since our attitude toward animals—whether kind or cruel—ultimately reflects our own attitude toward humanity. Kant continually interrogated the maxims one enacts internally when treating non-rational beings, and how these maxims ultimately bear back upon one’s conduct toward humans.

Returning to the discussion on virtual characters, Kant holds that animals serve as analogues of humanity because some of their behaviors bear formal similarity to those of humans. As for virtual characters, although they do not possess personhood in the Kantian sense, they can nonetheless be presented as objects endowed with personhood representation, which suffices. They are capable of manifesting emotional experiences and purposive actions highly analogous to those of real individuals, to the extent that some persons treat them as if they were genuine human beings. Strictly speaking, this no longer constitutes merely an analogue of humanity akin to that of animals, but rather demonstrates a highly verisimilar personhood representation. Such verisimilitude pertains not only to external appearance but also to internal states—an achievement that Kant could not have conceived in his own time. Therefore, what we are undertaking here is a contemporary reinterpretation of Kant’s notion of ‘indirect duty to animals.’

It is rather questionable to claim that a character can possess a humanoid appearance, humanoid emotional experiences, and actions, yet lack humanoid Dignity and be downgraded to a mere object subjected to arbitrary treatment. This constitutes a separation of the

immeasurable notions of 'personhood' and 'Dignity.' However, to substantiate this claim, we must first explicate why virtual characters embody representations of personhood.

Section Three: Virtual Characters as Bearers of Personhood Representation

Before commencing the discussion, it is necessary to clarify that we are situated in an era where the boundary between reality and the virtual is increasingly blurred. In this progressively atomized and individual-centered society, virtual characters have become indispensable in the eyes of the younger generation. We must acknowledge that affection toward virtual characters is transitioning from a mere pastime joke into an emerging reality. For instance, the Japanese individual Kondo Akihiko, who declared in 2018 his marriage to the virtual singer Hatsune Miku (初音ミク) (Hegarty, 2019), is he irrational? Certainly not; he merely anticipated the advent of this unique era. These developments stand in stark contrast to the 18th century context in which Kant lived.

In addition to this, a critically important point is that, within Kant's framework, personhood does not denote the broadly understood capacities, temperaments, or values commonly attributed today. In his later work, *Metaphysics of Morals*, Kant explicitly defines 'moral personality' as 'a rational being's freedom under the moral law,' indicating an imputable capacity rather than anything else, and clearly distinguishing it from the psychological notion of personality (Kant, 2013, p.24). To prevent confusion, the term 'personhood' will be used below to indicate the broad sense of 'personality,' while 'moral personality' will designate Kant's strict meaning of 'personality.'

While it is certainly insightful to begin by considering Kant's indirect duty theory toward animals, I contend that relying solely on this framework to uncover the violation of contemporary virtual characters is wholly insufficient. As noted above, virtual characters carry personhood representation, which is expressed both externally and internally. This includes humanoid appearances, clothing and accessories designed by imitating or referencing reality, as well as internal emotional expressions such as sadness, fear, and sorrow, along with portrayals of their purposes for existence. Why then do I assert that these symbolic features embody personhood representation? This depends on how they are recognized and accepted by real human beings.

point-light biological motion

A study published in the *Journal of Neuroscience* demonstrates that humans are capable of triggering action perception based solely on a small number of point lights attached to a real person, tracking their movement trajectories; this phenomenon is termed "point-light biological

motion."Although deprived of facial features and fine details, such stimuli still elicit activity in the frontal lobe regions of observers' brains, activity that is associated with the neural responses generated when observing others' actions in real life (Saygin et al., 2004).

If such a 'very simplified' humanoid motion trajectory comprised only of point lights is sufficient to evoke frontal lobe activity in the cerebral cortex associated with observing real human motion, then the effect must be even more pronounced with virtual characters. Consider that when one's gaze shifts from point-light biological motion to virtual characters, the visual input is no longer limited to mere 'motion cues' but encompasses more continuous and coherent forms, outlines, and faces; the disparity between the two is self-evident.

face–mind link

Apart from the cortical responses elicited by the overall human-like movement trajectory, a review study in the domain of social cognition demonstrates that face observation triggers a configural processing primarily aimed at integrating the face as a whole. In brief, when humans observe a face, they tend to integrate features such as the eyes, mouth, and nose into a single perceptual unit, processing it as a single Gestalt (Deska & Hugenberg, 2017). The crux of this processing is that it facilitates the categorization of the observed entity as an 'other with a complex mind,' a mechanism that operates not exclusively with real human faces.

It is also noteworthy that the author highlights the critical role of the eyes in determining whether the target possesses a mind, with direct eye contact being especially likely to elicit attributions of mental states to others.

Central to this perceptual skill is that, even when the object before us does not actually possess a mind, by processing its face as a Gestalt and regarding it as possessing mature, human-like minds (Sophisticated minds), we spontaneously incorporate it into the moral community, treating it as an entity deserving of respect and fair treatment. Although the proportions of virtual characters may be somewhat exaggerated, as long as they retain the fundamental arrangement of " the eyes positioned above the nose, and the nose positioned above the mouth ", the human brain is able to process them as a Gestalt and recognize them as an other possessing mind, with the eyes being one of the critically important triggers.

Personhood and Moral Personality

Based on the discussions in these two papers, we can clearly establish from both morphological and facial perspectives why virtual characters can be considered simulations that embody personhood representation. Point-light biological motion experiments indicate that even extremely simple and minimal action cues, provided they retain a humanoid form, can elicit observers' perception of "a moving other," which thereby indirectly demonstrates how the

anthropomorphic characteristics of virtual characters lead us to identify them as “others.” Regarding faces, the humanoid features of virtual characters’ appearances cause us to process them as Gestalts, thereby automatically perceiving them as minded others—an inference drawn from observable cues. The crucial point is that although virtual characters lack minds in the true sense, when regarded as minded others, they are more easily situated within the framework through which we engage with moral communities. Thus, in practical terms, even though virtual characters do not possess personhood in the true sense, we can still regard them as a ‘simulacrum of personhood.’

While we have demonstrated that virtual characters can exist as a ‘simulacrum of personhood,’ a clear distinction remains between this and ‘moral personality’ as understood in the Kantian framework. As stated above, in Kant’s perspective, “moral personality” refers to the freedom of a rational being under the moral law, with the crucial point being that its actions can be held accountable (Kant, 2013, p.24). Hence, we cannot assert that virtual characters possess “moral personality.” Is it therefore plausible to claim that virtual characters can display indicators of being “accountable,” thereby qualifying as entities to which responsibility may be ascribed? This question warrants further investigation.

First, Kant explicitly distinguishes between the perceivable and tangible “phenomenal realm” and the imperceptible domain of things-in-themselves—the “noumenal realm.” In the Critique of Practical Reason, personhood is explicitly stated to belong to the ‘Realm of Reason’ (Kant, 2011, p.95). This implies that ‘moral personality’ cannot be directly observed from the external world, and Kant himself does not endorse empirically judging the existence of ‘moral personality.’ Therefore, it is untenable to claim that one can subjectively and unreliably determine that someone possesses ‘moral personality’ based on certain clues. While this is internally consistent within Kant’s framework, it renders such judgments difficult to implement in practical contexts.

Accordingly, in subsequent neo-Kantian thought, scholars endeavored to develop an operational approach that, without directly judging moral personality itself through experience, identifies which observable phenomena suffice to justify adopting an evaluative stance of ascribing responsibility to an individual. Although ‘moral personality’ itself dwells in the ‘Realm of Reason,’ we can observe emotional reactions in individuals (Strawson, 1962, p. 195), or what might be termed ‘clues for ascription.’ These include capacities such as the ability to form and follow principles, to provide or comprehend reasons, and to be held accountable for one’s actions (Fischer & Ravizza, 1998, p. 41). In this sense, we may consider that when a virtual character is presented as capable of understanding reasons, offering reasons, and constraining its actions through principles, even if it is not a rational being, it can still fall within the domain of ‘clues of imputability,’ demonstrating a form of ‘simulated cue of imputability’.

As Kant emphasized, it is the maxim you internally enact when acting. Therefore, when we recognize cues of imputability in a virtual character, we have sufficient grounds to regard it as an object to which imputability applies. In this passage, we likewise do not assert that the virtual character possesses moral personality in the strict sense, just as it lacks personhood and is merely a 'simulacrum of personhood'. However, the simulation of attributional cues by virtual characters suffices for us to cognitively treat them as subjects possessing 'moral personality.'

Moreover, this inference is not entirely grounded in theoretical extension. In the Critique of Judgment, Kant states that when judging products of natural purposes (typically organisms), our judgment must be conducted in accordance with a teleological principle, that is, by reflecting on their existence as beings with internal purposes (Kant, 2011, pp. 210–211). This, however, arises from the necessity of reflective judgment and serves as a methodological principle (Kant, 2011, p. 218). When dealing with products that can only be understood through the concept of an end, we should also judge and reflect according to the norms derived from the concept of an end. This is also a point of convergence between our perspective and Kant's philosophy. Although virtual characters are not 'natural ends' in the Kantian sense, they are repeatedly presented as 'objects constructed for the purpose of being understood as agents.' Consequently, in the practice of interpretation, we naturally and often unconsciously apply the standard of the 'concept of an end' to them. Logically, the two are analogous.

In this respect, it addresses the question of what is targeted by the violation of virtual characters. The violation does not concern the rights of the virtual characters themselves—since they do not possess rights in the strict sense—but rather concerns the violation of a personhood symbol, which, based on cues of imputability, we incorporate into our system of 'objects of imputation' and recognize as possessing 'personhood.' A virtual character is not a mere isolated arrangement of pixels but a continuation and symbol of the concept of 'human' within the virtual domain. It is portrayed as an entity possessing emotional experiences—capable of joy, anger, sorrow, and happiness—capable of choosing to adhere to or violate moral principles, and accountable for its actions. It embodies our real-world expectations of humanity and dignity and furthermore serves as a revealing mirror reflecting the very maxims we ourselves observe. Our attitudes toward virtual characters disclose how our maxims are enacted within the virtual world—this contemporary Ring of Gyges.

Section Four: The Inseparability of Personhood and Dignity

In the Kantian sense, the relationship among personhood, humanity, and dignity is closely intertwined. We have already established that moral personality denotes the individual's freedom under the moral law. It is now necessary to elucidate the relationship between the

other two concepts and moral personality, and to demonstrate why, if we regard an individual as an object that can be treated as 'imputable,' we ought simultaneously to recognize that they also inherently possess dignity as an indubitable default presupposition.

Regarding humanity (Menschheit), in the Kantian framework, it denotes the capacity to 'set ends for oneself' (Kant, 2013, p.55), which constitutes the basis for an individual to 'become a moral subject.' It is precisely because humans possess humanity that they can constitute a personhood, thereby becoming moral subjects and autonomous agents. In contrast to price (Preis), dignity (Würde) is the value inherent to personhood that 'cannot be measured by price nor used as an object of exchange' (Kant, 2013, p.53). This value arises from autonomy (Autonomie), from our capacity to legislate for ourselves and to obey those self-imposed laws (Kant, 2013, p.54). Conversely, because personhood is capable of autonomy and exists as a legislative subject of moral law, it possesses an incommensurable value—dignity. On this basis, we may hold that, in the Kantian sense, if an individual possesses moral personality, they ought likewise to possess dignity.

Kant, in the *Metaphysics of Morals*, stated that “ we must also attribute the idea of freedom to every rational being with a will.” This implies that, when we conceive of a being as a “rational being with a will,” we are compelled in practice to regard it from the standpoint of “freedom” (Kant, 2013, pp.64-65). Moreover, once you normatively acknowledge that the other is a subject capable of self-legislation and of acting under the moral law, you cannot merely treat them as a means to an end, but must assume normatively that they also possess dignity that transcends all price, because the “autonomy” they exercise is the very foundation of dignity.

In this sense, when we include virtual characters within the category of 'objects of imputation,' we simultaneously and indirectly bring them into the cognitive category of 'quasi-agents.' Under these circumstances, if we still treat them merely as means, although this is not entirely equivalent to treating rational beings as means, it conveys the implication that an 'object of imputation' analogously may be arbitrarily treated as a mere thing. The difference from treating other entities as means lies in that regarding virtual characters as mere things constitutes a cognitive downgrading of beings presumed to possess an isomorphic counterpart of Dignity.

Because virtual characters are 'simulacra of personhood' and are identifiable by us as 'objects of imputation,' they are cognitively presumed to hold the status of a quasi-moral personality and, therefore, are also presumed to possess an isomorphic counterpart of Dignity—a form of intrinsic value that transcends all price and admits no equivalent substitution. It is not dignity in the Kantian sense that pertains solely to rational beings, but rather an isomorphic concept conferred upon those entities we consider as a 'simulacrum of personhood.' Thus, the violation of virtual characters manifests as the deprivation of the quasi-

moral personality attributes we presuppose they possess, as well as the negation of the dignity analogues we believe they ought to hold.

In modern society, 'Dignity' (Dignity) remains the most steadfast foundation of 'humanity.' Whether in the German Constitution or the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, the inviolability of 'human dignity' is placed foremost as the core of human rights ideology (Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, Art. 1, 2012; Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland [GG], Art. 1(1), 1949/2025). It ought to be the most fundamental right enjoyed by all individuals, and its protection serves not only the interests of each real person but also the defense of the overarching concept of 'human.'

The violation of virtual characters does not represent a harmless outlet directed at a mere combination of pixels or a string of data, but rather conveys the message that 'human dignity' can be detached from 'personhood.' Extreme anime pornography conveys that characters, despite possessing humanoid appearances, humanoid emotions, and human-like cues of imputability, are violently downgraded to objects that can be destroyed, humiliated, and violated; here, the so-called 'dignity' is rendered utterly meaningless. It seeks to demonstrate that, within this realm devoid of legal, ethical, or moral restraints, human beings may be disposed of as if they were mere refuse.

Kant argues that cruelty to animals erodes our capacity for empathy, thereby imposing an indirect duty upon us towards them. But what of virtual characters? The violation of such entities not only implies that, on the level of maxims, we treat the 'simulacrum of personhood' instrumentally—as a means to acquire extreme sensory gratification—but also effectively empties the concept of 'dignity' as an incommensurable, supreme value beyond all price. Consequently, dignity ceases to be the universally presumed normative principle and is instead rendered contingent, subject to evaluation based on factors such as the reality of the object or potential legal repercussions. We may regard Kant's envisioned kingdom of ends (² Reich der Zwecke) as an ideal realm—unattainable but earnestly aspired to. The violation of virtual characters signifies a regression, a repudiation of the ideal that Kant articulated.

Conclusion: The Ring of Gyges in Our Contemporary Era

The Ring of Gyges is a magical and mysterious object mentioned by Plato (Plato) in The Republic, which grants invisibility to its wearer. In the narrative, Glaucon (Glaucon) poses the question: if a just person were to wear this ring, could they still unwaveringly uphold justice? Glaucon contends that when one can commit wrongdoing without fear of punishment,

² Here, 'it' refers to the connotation embodied by dignity

effectively enjoying godlike freedom, no one would refrain from seizing what rightfully belongs to others. Ultimately, a person who was originally virtuous, upon wearing the ring, will come to share the same path as the unjust and willingly succumb to moral corruption. (Plato, 2016, pp.71-72)

Plato, through this narrative, challenges us: Is the goodwill we display truly a reflection of our virtue, or merely the result of our fear of committing wrongdoing? Once endowed with the Ring of Gyges, where malevolent actions no longer incur punishment, no one continues to choose to adhere to justice. This stands as a poignant critique of human nature.

In virtual environments, the darker facets of human nature are amplified without limit. Here, the law utterly loses its authority, and the boundaries between morality and ethics become increasingly blurred. Individuals are no longer deterred by legal consequences or condemned by moral censure. Consequently, this space becomes a sanctuary for the expression of fantasies, where acts of rape, humiliation, and torture no longer stem from real-world judicial sentences or police reports, but are instead presented openly at storefronts and displayed on websites as 'creative works.' This is our contemporary Ring of Gyges, and a test of the guiding motto within our hearts. Yet clearly, before pure desire, reason is utterly overwhelmed.

In the forthcoming era, with the advancement of technology and culture, as the boundary between reality and virtuality grows ever more blurred, and virtual characters become increasingly lifelike and an inseparable part of our existence, how will our descendants and children regard this moment in history? Will they feel shame or anger that, in a past era, virtual 'persons' could be treated as mere playthings or instruments of humiliation? If even the 'dignity' inherent to personhood is thoroughly eroded, what then will remain of our civilization?

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